

LINGUOCULTURE FOCUSES ON THE HUMAN ASPECT

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Abstract: Linguoculture focuses on the human aspect, or more specifically, the cultural factor in man, according to G.G. Sloskin. The Linguoculturology Center's status as a cultural phenomenon demonstrates the anthropological paradigm's influence on human science.

While there is agreement over the subject of linguoculturalology, there are differing opinions. For instance, linguoculturology, in the words of V.N. Telia, only examines the relationship that exists simultaneously between language and culture. According to V.A. Maslova, this area investigates language in both synchronous and diachronic ways. While V.A. Maslova argues that the linguocultural characteristics of the language of a particular people or group of related peoples should be examined independently, V.N. Telia also underlines the universal nature of the subject of linguoculture.

Key words: Metaphor, method, culture, culture

Introduction

Particularly in Russian linguistics, linguistics is one of the most developed areas in the world today, and several textbooks have been produced in this field. According to linguists, the most well-known of these is the textbook written by V.A. Maslova. This textbook includes instances of linguocultural analysis of a specific language unit, as well as methodologies, object and topic, and directions in the field of linguoculture.

Research on linguistics and culture is evident in the following areas:

- 1) The linguo-cultural characteristics of a specific speech genre. It frequently addresses mythology and the vocabulary of folklore genres;
- 2) it examines how a linguistic notion is expressed in a work created in a certain style. It mostly examines fiction language analysis;
- 3) comparative work. Here, mainly linguistic units in Russian are compared with English, German, French;
- 4) aspects of linguoculturology related to pedagogical science. The main goal is to develop students' skills in identifying and analyzing linguoculturological units.

In Uzbek linguistics, studies using the linguocultural approach have started to surface in recent decades. For instance, the study of feeling in Uzbek and French,

or the national and cultural elements of moral and educational texts, is the focus of Z.I. Solieva's dissertation. The paper "In search of ways to perfect the study of language" by Professor N. Mahmudov offers a thorough and well-founded explanation of the fundamental issues with the anthropocentric paradigm in linguoculture as a whole. This essay, which includes thoughtful observations on linguoculture, may be regarded as the first in Uzbek linguistics. The paper offers extremely well-founded insights about the elements that went into creating linguoculturological theory, the fundamental ideas within it, and the variations in how those ideas are interpreted. One of the most crucial ideas in the subject, which N. Mahmudov writes about in particular, is language and culture: does not show at all. [1:78]

Typically, language and culture refer to (or rather, to the interpretation of a language via the study of) a culture, or alternatively, to the study of a culture, or more specifically, linguoculturalogy's definition of culture. The collection of achievements of human civilization in production, social and spiritual-enlightenment life (Uzbek culture), not the level (culture of speech) attained in intellectual-spiritual or economic activity. Regarding the linguistics component of the text, it should be mentioned that the text is one of the research subjects for linguoculturalology, together with other language units. In this sense, V.A. Maslova, the author of "Linguoculturology," writes: "The text is a real crossroads of linguistics and culture." Text is, after all, both the pinnacle of linguistic phenomena and an application of cultural life. The study of language as the expression of cultural values is known as linguoculture. [2:54]

Notable is also V.A. Maslova's viewpoint, particularly with regard to parallels in texts. The scientist restates the importance of parallels in the production of the text, stating that they serve as a way of assuring the text's coherence as well as its structural and compositional functions. Findings imply that whereas metaphors—analogies and condensed forms—may have significant cognitive-semantic value in the text, they may also represent facets of the speakers' national-cultural perspectives. Metaphor-based texts also enable us to recognize language-specific textual forms, which may be assessed as antecedent forms of text. The prior text issue is another textual phenomena in linguistics. O.E. Artemova, a scholar, claims that antecedent genres serve as "accumulators" of cultural knowledge. [3:76]

Sentiment is another problem with the text in linguistics. A sentence communicates intertextuality and serves as a moral and pedagogical language unit.

Comparatively examining the national and cultural characteristics of English and Uzbek sentiments, Z.I. Salieva views the author's altered presentation of didactic ideas in the writings of intellectuals who were influential in a given nation's history as an example of intertextuality. The researcher uses the didactic texts that Navi narrates in Oybek's novel "Navoi" as an example. This characteristic is present in numerous Uzbek-language works. It is well known that linguoculture holds a unique position for the idea of the global linguistic landscape, which was first presented to linguistics by L. Weisgerber. The universe's linguistic landscape is a language-sealed framework of reality perception unique to a given linguistic community, a universal but simultaneously nationally customized method of understanding and comprehending the cosmos. Every natural language in the cosmos has its own linguistic landscape. The most significant source for the scientific interpretation of the linguistic environment of a certain ethnic world, in our opinion, is the analysis of texts that include metaphors, text-metaphors, precedent units, standards, and speech labels. [4:78]

Conclusion

The major focus in global linguistics is not only on the semantics of a word, but also on its pragmatic meaning, evaluation connection, national cultural elements, and the link between the term and the speech of a specific topic. Gaining a greater grasp of a nation's spiritual legacy, rich history, national values, and cultural and spiritual resources may be achieved via studying the essence of language. Foreign language instruction is currently being offered in more schools and colleges than ever before. New curriculum, new disciplines, and new training areas are being established in response to this. Studying foreign languages has become essential in the current world as we are constantly interacting with two, three, or more different cultures. [5:98]

References:

1. Bekiyeva, M. J. (2020). Lingvokulturologiyaning tadqiqot obyekti, predmeti, maqsadi va vazifalari. Интернаука.
2. BEKIYEVA, M. (2020). Bekiyeva Malika O „ZBEK TILINIKOGNITIV O „RGANISH OMILLARI, VAZIFALARI VA AHAMIYATI. Архив исследований.
3. Bekiyeva, M.J. (2021) konseptning lingvokulturologiyadagi bazaviy kategoriyalardan biri. Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире. <https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=4>.
4. BEKIYEVA, M. (2020). MALIKA BEKIYEVA INGLIZ VA O „ZBEK TILLARIDAGI FRAZELOGIK BIRLIKLARNING DUNYONING KOGNITIV TASVIRIDAGI O „RNI. Архив исследований. BEKIYEVA, M. (2020).

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